

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

«INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN CONSTRUCTION,
CIVIL ENGINEERING, AND ARCHITECTURE»

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

OCTOBER 20–21, 2025
DNIPRO, UKRAINE

Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine
Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies
ESI “Prydniprovsk State Academy of Civil Engineering and Architecture”
NGO “Academy of Construction of Ukraine”
Dnipropetrovsk Regional Branch of the National Union
of Ukrainian Architects
PCAE “Stroitel-P”
Prat Avp “Sodruzhestvo”

Abstracts of the XX International Scientific
and Practical Conference

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN CONSTRUCTION, CIVIL ENGINEERING AND ARCHITECTURE

*Dedicated to the 95th anniversary of Prydniprovsk State Academy
of Civil Engineering and Architecture*

October 20–21, 2025
Dnipro, Ukraine

ISBN: 978-617-8314-77-4
UDC 658.589:620.9:72:681.5
M 34

Abstracts of the XX International Scientific and Practical Conference “Innovative Technologies in Construction, Civil Engineering and Architecture” (October, 20–21, 2025): edited by Kostiantyn SUKHYYI, Mykola SAVYTSKYI, Yurii PROIDAK, Vladyslav DANISHEVSKYY. Dnipro : ESI PSACEA, 2025, 414 p. (e-edition)

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The Conference is held in the frame of the international projects Horizon Europe “ENERGENIUS” (id 101160720), Horizon 2020 “EffectFact” (id 101008140), Erasmus 2027 “The Bridge” (id 101127884), Erasmus 2027 “UKRENERGY” (id 101082898) and is dedicated to the 95th anniversary of Prydniprovsk State Academy of Civil Engineering and Architecture.

Approved for publication by the Scientific Council of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies (minutes no. 1 of 24.09.2025).

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UDC 001.891:620.9:681.518:004.9

USE OF DIGITAL TWIN AND GAMIFICATION TO EMPOWER CITIZENS ENABLING A SMOOTH ENERGY TRANSITION AND PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE BEHAVIOURS WITH ENERGENIUS

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Abstract. The ENERGENIUS project, co-funded by Horizon Europe programme, reimagines how citizens, businesses, and communities interact with energy. By integrating cutting-edge digital tools, AI-driven insights, gamification, and expertise from 9 cross-sectorial data spaces called “knowledge arenas”, ENERGENIUS empowers users to make smarter energy choices.

Problem Statement. The energy transition requires not only technological innovation but also policy reform, consumer engagement and behavioural change [1]. To this end, in 2015 the Energy Union framework strategy [2] envisions that citizens spearhead the energy transition, benefit from novel technologies, and actively participate in the market. Additionally, the concept of the 'energy citizen', introduced by the BRIDGE CCE WG [3] in May 2022, encapsulates the roles and responsibilities in the consumer-actor relationship within the energy sector for building a clean, fair, and inclusive European energy system. In October 2022, the EU action plan for Digitalizing the Energy System [4] assigns great importance to creating digital services that meet the needs, skills, conditions, habits and expectations of different categories of participants, following a “leave no one behind” strategy, stating that “there is no transition towards clean energy without a plan for digital”.

Research Objective. ENERGENIUS provides an innovative pathway dedicated to cultivating an inclusive, community-driven energy transition, firmly aligned to the ethos of 'Leave No One Behind'.

ENERGENIUS adopts a multi-disciplinary approach that integrates a) cutting-edge Digital Tools and Services, b) a Symbiotic Ecosystem, c) Innovative Engagement Methods and d) a secure, interoperable and scalable Data and Service Framework. The project is shaping a holistic omni-channel experience with the citizens at the centre.

At its core is ENERGENIUS Suite, a one-stop-shop digital platform providing a wide range of interlinked services, including digital twin models, serious games, cross-sectorial dashboards, marketplace and AI-driven recommendations. This robust ecosystem integrates data not only from the energy sector but also across other sectors (e.g.: healthcare, mobility and tourism). The goal is to deliver customized AI-powered solutions for energy efficiency and sustainability.

Research Results. Two of the tools to be developed in ENERGENIUS are Scan to Digital Twin (S2DT) and ENERGENIUS PLAY (ENPLAY) which will be presented below.

The S2DT produces an accurate virtual 3D replica of the user’s home and associated energy devices. By employing advanced scanning technologies such as LiDAR and photogrammetry, coupled with AI-driven reconstruction algorithms, S2DT captures complex details of residential 3D models and energy setups and converts them into dynamic digital twins. A distinctive innovation of this tool is its privacy-by-design approach. The scanning system will automatically ignore any human being or any other object not part of energy consumption.

To maximize engagement, the 3D model output of the S2DT is augmented with the ENPLAY, a serious game that lets players move inside the 3D replica of their own homes and engage in real-world energy management scenarios that deepen their understanding of energy usage and of its impacts.

ENPLAY, a tool designed for citizens, creates an engaging and educational experience that empowers individuals to participate in energy management and sustainability activities. Through immersive simulations and interactive scenarios, users gain a comprehensive understanding of energy consumption patterns, and their environmental impacts. By making informed decisions within the virtual environment, citizens can experiment with various strategies to reduce energy consumption, adopt renewable sources, and optimize their home setups.

These innovative tools are integrated with the advanced AI algorithms of the GURU, the project AI advisory tool which assists users with personalized energy recommendations and investment strategies to achieve energy efficiency. The combination of precise digital twinning and gamified learning empowers individuals, promotes energy-conscious behaviours and strengthens collective responsibility, enabling citizens to contribute to a greener and more resilient energy future.

Conclusions. ENERGENIUS envisions a future where every citizen is at the heart of the energy transition. The project aims to make energy management inclusive, ensuring equal access to tools and resources for individuals, businesses, and communities. By combining sustainability, technology, and engagement, ENERGENIUS democratizes energy solutions, driving efficiency, awareness, and adoption of renewable energy sources (RES) across Europe.

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